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USE OF I-131 AFTER SURGERY IN PATIENTS WITH DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER: AN INFLUENCE OF GENDER

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Abstract

Background: Differentiated thyroid cancer (DTC) is a common malignancy and is increasing in incidence. Although, patients with DTC have a good prognosis, recidive development can negatively affect their prognosis. The aim of this experimental study was to gain more information about DTC recidive occurring.

Study design: This study was performed using Surveillance Epidemiology among 300 patients, diagnosed with DTC, that undergo thyroid surgery.

Methods: The demographic, clinical and pathological characteristics of selected patients were compared. Also, correlation between age at the operation (AO) and age at the moment of recidive (AR) with years after operation when recidive occurred was performed.

Results: Years of patients ranged from 9 to 79. Mean and median ages in our study were the same, 44 years. Majority of patients 85.6% (257 patients) were female. A 110 patients have received I-131 treatment after surgery. Recidive have occurred in 32 patients, 11 male (OR= 3,86) and 17 female (OR=1.93). At the moment of recidive diagnose, years of patients ranged from 16 to 80. Mean age was 51,74 while median was 53 years. Pearson r was -0,03, for correlation between AO and years after operation when recidive occurred, and 0,1 for correlation between AR and years after operation when recidive occurred.

Conclusion: This experimental study indicate that recidives more frequently occurs in male which indicates the need for more aggressive treatment of this diseases in male. Additionally, there was no correlation between AO and AR with time that will past after operation before recidive occurred.

Keywords

Differentiated thyroid cancer, recidive, I-131